

Nanomaterial Fabricated Patch Antenna for Super High Frequency Applications

A Synopsis submitted to
Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka

For the degree of
Doctor of Science (D.Sc)

under
Under College of Engineering & Technology

Submitted by,
Dr.Ambresh Prabhakar Ambalgi
(Registration no.: 20SUDSC002)
March 2020

“Nanomaterial Fabricated Patch Antenna for Super High Frequency Applications”

Outline of the proposed research work

The great deal of research work is carried out so far is to increase the performance characteristics of microwave antennas for lower frequency, mid frequency band and super high frequency band wireless applications. The design aspect and its characterizations are also studied in detail for lower frequency, mid frequency band and super high frequency band wireless applications. The underlying principles involved in improving the performance characteristics of antenna are in wide context but to describe it in one example is that, to create additional resonance (multi-resonance antenna using nanomaterials with DGS concept) which has capacitive component with that of the other structure on the patch and feed element design. The antennas which will be designed and studied are well suited and resonated for the fixed design frequency in order to cope up with the applications of the wireless communication for lower frequency, mid frequency band and super high frequency band. The other parameters are also considered and studied such as VSWR, Radiation pattern, Gain, Return loss etc. When considering all these parameters, there was a trade-off between these parameters as to when, one factor performance increases other factor performance decreases hence, the antennas were designed in such as way that, it mitigated the trade-off and kept the performance towards a better acceptable level suitable for the wireless applications. Also in this present work, the concept of novel DGS (defected ground structure) multifunctional patch antennas fabricated on glass epoxy material coated with nanomaterials are designed, developed which are found to be rare in literature review are studied and carried out for wireless applications which have improved the performance compared to the previously available antennas.

Methodology used

The antennas are designed and fabricated using nanomaterials with DGS concept for different frequencies and are studied practically using microwave experimental setup.

Microwave experimental setup: The microwave experimental setup for the measurement of various parameters of microstrip patch antenna is used. The antenna parameters such as VSWR, impedance matching, return loss, radiation pattern etc are recorded and studied. The various components and equipments under this are, a) **DUT:** device under test (DUT) is connected in the receiving mode and the reference antenna (i.e. standard pyramidal horn) fed by Gunn source through microwave bench is kept in the transmitting mode at certain distance satisfying the formula $R = 2D^2/\lambda$, where R is the distance between transmitting and receiving antenna, D is the broadside dimension of the horn antenna and λ is the free space wavelength in *cm*. The transmitting and receiving antennas are aligned properly before taking the measurements to avoid the unwanted reflections. The microwave source at the transmitting section is energized for the operating frequency of microstrip antenna under test. b) **Turn table:** The turn table arrangement is used to measure the radiation pattern of rectangular microstrip antennas. In this arrangement, two antennas are placed so as to face each other and then, keeping the position of transmitting antenna fixed and receiving antenna is rotated around its axis to change the angle in steps of 10° degrees. The device under test (DUT) is connected in the receiving mode and the reference antenna (i.e. standard pyramidal horn) fed by Gunn source through microwave bench is kept in the transmitting mode at certain distance satisfying the formula $R = 2D^2/\lambda$. The transmitting and receiving antennas are aligned properly before taking the measurements to avoid the unwanted reflections. The microwave source at the transmitting section is energized for the operating frequency of rectangular microstrip antenna under test. **VNA:** An important feature of the VNA is the substantial

improvement in accuracy made possible with error correcting software for the measurement of antenna parameters practically.

The radio frequency measurements are carried out in anechoic chamber facility. The antenna fabrication is done using the standard photolithographic procedures. The simulation studies of the antennas are carried out using the licensed Mentor graphics *Zeland IE3D* simulation software. The intended design procedure for developing the microstrip patch antennas is as follows:

- Selection of essential parameters,
- Determine patch dimension and feed network using software and using the practical design analysis,
- also designing an antenna that can give accurate readings in different environments,
- Simulate and analyze the designed antenna,
- Construct the antenna on simulation platform,
- Construction & fabrication of antenna based on best simulation optimised parameter & results,
- Take antenna measurements using VNA/PNA/Handheld analyzers,
- Generate radiation pattern using near-field probe,
- Compare measured results with the theoretical results/simulated results,
- study antenna theory by building novel DGS microstrip patch antennas for wireless applications.

The expected outcome of the Work,

The primary objective/expected outcome of the research is the development of a novel type Microstrip Patch Antennas suitable for Wireless Applications with improved characteristics. Towards achieving this goal, investigations are carried out on different Patch configurations.

-Study of nanomaterial and its composites, Design of DGS multifunctional Microstrip patch antennas & the DGS Microstrip patch Antenna (with nanomaterial) for different shapes, configurations.

- Practical analysis of the designed Microstrip Patch Antenna with different nanomaterials.

- validate the predicted data through simulation and experiment (or calculation).

- Obtaining of the better radiation pattern, gain, VSWR, Return loss, Power levels etc.

- ascertain the influence of the geometrical and material parameters upon the radiation behaviour of the antenna.

- Development and testing of the optimized high gain antennas in the Anechoic chamber testing facility.

- To investigate the function of an antenna that can give accurate readings in different environmental conditions.

- develop compact designs DGS Microstrip patch Antenna configurations suitable for lower frequency, mid frequency band and super high frequency Wireless Applications.

Research results are framed in the form research paper and the same will be communicated and published in the UGC recognized journals. The work has also focussed on the design and such developed antennas which will be Patented further.

Specifically highlighting in what respect the research will advance the knowledge in the particular field of his Post-Doctoral work.

We are in an industry where everything is changing rapidly at faster rate, and if we focus on the design of antennas, we see that increasingly we are looking for smaller dimensions with better features of it. In this issue, we can highlight the antennas with microstrip design with DGS structure that are becoming more and more popular in wireless sectors such as mobile phones, satellite or more recently as object recognition. Among the advantages of this type of antenna, we can emphasize its low cost, small size, low profile, easy to manufacture and easy to implement, along with its disadvantages such as narrow bandwidth and low gain.

The foreword concerning, i.e., many researchers are carrying out the research in various fields of patch antennas so as to develop an antenna that has to overcome the disadvantages related to the conventional patch antenna/other types of antennas.

The proposed and designed antennas can be used for the applications such as LAN, WLAN, WiMax, IEEE802.11a, HiPERLAN/2, Cordless Phones, fixed wireless etc., in practical sense. It can also be aimed for the possible designing of the antenna for the operation at dedicated band of frequency by changing its design parameters like substrate, thickness of substrate, feed, geometry etc. Some of the antennas can also be used for application in the field of agriculture, health area. For ex: RFID antennas, RFID tags for patients etc.

In India, a variety of antenna research has been in process and still ongoing, starting from typical industrial level to advanced level miniaturized (both indoor and outdoor environment), tele-operation need, RADAR etc.

Various Proposed Antenna Outcomes obtained

The focus of this work was to study new and improved microstrip patch antenna (MSA) designs and investigate them with different techniques adopted to develop and match with their applications in wireless domain.

The effective working of antennas is researched and interpreted in the form of results as being effective in wide range of wireless frequency band applications. The key parameters (such as curves of return loss, radiation patterns, gain, antenna performance, impedance map, VSWR, and phase plot) that affect architecture and applications were studied and understood their implications. The designed slot antennas, numerous type antennas, microstrip patch antennas are worked at the optimal frequency and power level. Various patch antennas (using IE3D design and analysis software) are simulated and the desired enhancement rate is reached. It is also established that, the results obtained through hardware development (various antennas) and analysis obtained using software are compared technically to the expected effects and are found to be nearly same.

The conventional MSA's and other antennas based on nanomaterials (Gold, Titanium oxide, Silver), flexible substrates are studied and developed for the various resonating frequencies f_r 's - 2.4 GHz, 3 GHz, 3.5 GHz, 6 GHz, 8 GHz and 9 GHz.

Theses patch antennas with novel slots introduced a capacitance that suppresses the inductance introduced by the feed due to the thick substrate and hence, multiple resonances due slots are obtained suitable for multiband applications using single antenna element. Also, the smith chart plots of various antennas clear illustrate that, the resonant frequencies points are similar to the middle impedance point 1 verifying improved matching properties among input and load.

The patch's sides, the calculated side measurements are preserved without modifying patch length and width, quarterwave transformer and feedline along with length, width remaining unchanged. Novel wider slots, slits on epoxy substrate, flexible substrate and coated with nanomaterials are designed and etched. Since; broad slots, slits relative to narrow slots, slits are more effective in bandwidth enhancement [1-Chap.2]. The measurements of patch and slot are known as a component of λ_0 , where wavelength is controlled by λ_0 . The results of novel slots are thus seen as an enhancement feature for the antenna functioning. The antennas are uniformly coated with nanomaterial such as Gold, Titanium oxide, Silver, which tends to have better conductivity compared to copper patch. These nanomaterials are used to enhance its conduction process of patch in order to achieve better performances.

EDSMSA-WMS has shown greater gains in bandwidth and its benefits compared with EDSMSA. In comparison, the result of new multi-slots engraved on the patch plane allows an elongated or improved surface excitation current path along the slot lengths and widths on the patch plane indicating a improved gain with impedance bandwidth having greater RL. The dielectric antenna mounted on epoxy dielectric substrate demonstrates the improved bandwidth with increase in its radiation properties also. The maximum bandwidth of antenna achieved was 124%.

The practical radiation patterns of the various antenna exhibited omni-directional shape pattern, doughnut shaped pattern and broadsided with linearly polarized characteristics in both E, H plane. The average resonating frequency gain measured is 13.30 dB. The gain is however increased due to the decreases in the excited patch's surface current path, resulting in a decrease in the antenna's efficiency factor and hence increase in the gain of antenna is seen. These antennas are effective in many wideband communications applications.

A successfully constructed circular microstrip patch antenna for the resonating frequency 2.4GHz with probe feed technique according to antenna requirements is tested employing IE3D electromagnetic simulation software. This 2.4GHz resonant frequency antenna, reached a bandwidth of 52.31MHz with return loss of -12.11 dB. The antenna output satisfies the required RL and VSWR specifications at the necessary operating frequency. This antenna considers its use in wireless applications for 2.4 GHz.

The goal was also to develop and conduct simulation analysis of circular microstrip patch antenna with simple single slot etched on the patch for resonating frequency of 3GHz. Some effect of disadvantages is minimized. Some factors are also involved in the selection of feeding technique. So, line feed technique was used here. After the whole analysis, the characteristics of proposed antenna are enhanced as seen by its parameters. The simulation result shows good agreement with practical values. Such antenna finds its application for wireless indoor application in S band.

For resonating frequency of 3.5GHz, a single band probe feed circular microstrip patch antenna has been studied and presented. The simulated results of RL characteristics, radiation pattern, VSWR pattern, current distribution pattern, Smith chart for resonant frequency 3.5 GHz are studied. This simulation is rendered using IE3D tools for electromagnetic analysis. The designed antenna has attained better impedance that suits predictable radiation pattern and fulfilled return loss. Among these antennas, the better one, found is for resonating frequency of 3.5 GHz because it has got a better efficiency, gain and better impedance bandwidth when compare to the rest of the antennas discussed.

Multi band antennas which were designed and developed have attained a significant improvement in impedance bandwidth, good RL, better VSWR and with improved radiation characterises which finds its application in C and X band frequency range.

The antennas are operating at multiband frequencies, gain much attention especially in L, S, C, X & Ka band wireless applications such as WiMax, RADAR, fixed satellite services, mobile maritime applications, WLAN and SAR in which two operating bands are used independently for transmit/receive operations. This work deals with the characteristic of Microstrip Antenna (MSA) and then count rates on the development in Microstrip Patch Antenna technology. New antenna configuration for improved performance is studied, discussed which is fabricated on flexible substrate and also by use of nanomaterials. Several methods are available in the literature relating to multi band antennas. But, the use and combination of various techniques such as, use of various slots, slits of different shapes, sizes having different dimensions that are fabricated on the patch plane, strip line feed technique for multiband operation and nanomaterials DGS method are found rarely in the literature. Further, study of embedding group of slots, use of circular patch, use of circular slotted patch, pentagon slotted patch, rhombus slot on patch plane, double rhombus slotted patch, single and double wide slot patch and other types as listed in this work are found rarely in the literature. In view of this, a detailed and systematic study is carried out to enhance the impedance bandwidth with good radiation characteristics, to achieve high gain of MSA and to reduce the loss using the above mentioned techniques.

Nanotechnology: Nanotechnology is characterized as the utilization of nano-science in innovative gadgets/forms/items. It is quick encouraging and innovation fit in practical for everyone in the areas of mechanical and customer products [1]. In 1959, the American Theoretical Scientist *Dr. Richard P. Feynman* introduced the first traditionally spoken concept about nanotechnology. Innovation of scanning tunnelling microscope in 1981 by IBM which is utilized to control singular particles and atoms, and disclosure of fullerene in 1985 prompts the development of nanotechnology. In 1974, Professor *Norio Taniguchi* of the Tokyo University of Science described the term "nanotechnology" as in paper: "*Nano-*

technology mainly consists of the processing of separation, consolidation, and deformation of materials by one atom or by one molecule”.

The absolute most progressive nanotechnology applications are interchange frameworks, nano useful gadgets, nano installed frameworks, nano utilitarian materials, semiconductor materials, nanomagnets, power module terminals, sun oriented cell and photonic materials and so forth [2]. Nanotechnology speaks to an expansive territory and is made out of nanomaterials using nanotools and nanodevices. Nanomaterials speak to a class of materials portrayed by an element size in the range 1-100 nm. While nanodevices will absolutely be produced using nanomaterials, nanomaterial itself impacts region past nanotechnology. It is significant that bringing the component size to 1 to 100 nm brings about noteworthy upgrade and significant enhancement of electrical, electronic, optical and attractive properties.

The accomplishments of nanostructured materials empowered specialists to investigate the physical and electronic properties for different applications in the field of nanoelectronics, nanooptics, vitality transformation and compound detecting. Compound sensors have significant applications in the territory of ecological checking, open security, car application and medicinal analysis. While a wide range of ways to deal electromechanical, paramagnetic, impetus based and so on are accessible and metal oxide, copper oxide, tin oxide are broadly utilized for a scope of a range of species [3] [4] [5]. Another territory of intrigue is investigation of nanotechnology empowered hardware in creating applications dependent on attractive nanomaterials, nano films, carbon nanotube and graphene. The electronic applications include microwave antennas, filters, inductors, chokes, core- shaped transformers, ultra high frequency telecommunications, data storage devices and so forth.

There are numerous nanotechnology devices accessible where nanomaterials are acknowledged into gadgets with elite. Regularly gadget manufacture requires affidavit of either nano composites (blend of metals, oxides and so on) or unadulterated metals on some sort of dielectric materials dependent on applications. For instance, thermal physical vapor deposition (PVD) system, radio frequency sputtering (RF-sputter), chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system to name few tools which are utilized for deposition of metal oxides or metals in nano thickness level on different materials like substrates, plastics, metals, silicon wafer and so forth. Some other nanotechnology apparatus are basic screen printing system, spray deposition, spin coating, dip coating technique, electro-spinning, inkjet printing etc are used to deposit nano composites other device fabrications and so forth are utilized to store nano composites other gadget manufactures. There are nanotechnology estimations instruments, for example, Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and so forth are utilized to gauge and break down nano molecule thickness, layer consistency, thin film consistency and so on at nano level. For electrical portrayal, for example, permittivity, permeability, conductivity, AC and DC resistance of fabricated device tools such as four probe technique, impedance analyzer, network analyzer etc are used.

For nanotechnology enabled electronic device fabrication, many material simulation tools are available. For example COMSOL multi-physics simulation software is used to model and analyze nano material behavior with respect to external factors such as temperature, pressure, stress etc at atomic and molecular level.

Benefits of Nanotechnology Enabled Antenna Development

- ✓ Miniaturization without affecting other parameters like radiation efficiency, directivity etc.
- ✓ Increasing bandwidth in multiple folds.

- ✓ Reducing density of antenna structure.
- ✓ Nano materials are best known for their highly superior mechanical properties linked with the increased material surface area contribution. This can be directly exploited in antenna technology to produce antennas fabricated on flexible substrates such as cotton, plastic and curved materials.
- ✓ It has been established in several nano-materials that mechanical properties like yield strength, tensile strength, fatigue etc show remarkable improvement over bulk materials. These desirable properties can be used in the development of mechanically robust electromagnetic sensors that operate effectively in harsh environments.

Nanomaterials with predominant electromagnetic properties will have high impact in defence application, medicinal services, cellular application and so on. In coming days, the greatest research in the business segment will be in the remote and correspondence industry. Considering the case of analog cellular communication systems, it is anticipated that market for redesigning existing low profile antenna in wireless system will be a boom in a few millions \$ every year.

The entire work reported in this thesis is mainly divided into five chapters, each chapter has been organized beginning with an introduction of the concerned chapter and detailed explanation related to the work.

The first chapter explains the introduction, history to microstrip patch antennas (MSAs), concept of nanotechnology, nanomaterials and its tools. A brief description on different types of excitation feed to MSAs, advantages and disadvantages, applications of MSAs etc are discussed followed by its references.

The second chapter deals with the elaborative literature survey/ review of past work. The review covers the period from 1983 to 2019 along with references.

The third chapter describes the various microwave components and equipment used in experimental setup and methodology adopted. The use of antenna turntable for the radiation pattern measurement of proposed antennas with some introduction to IE3D simulation software is also discussed in this chapter with its references.

The design considerations of rectangular MSAs, design of slots, design of slits, nanomaterial fabricated MSAs, MSAs using flexible substrates, design of feed and fabrication process and various experimental, simulation results are measured and reported for the proposed antennas in the chapter four. The discussions are made on the study of bandwidth of antennas, effect of slots, different slotted techniques, nanomaterial (gold, silver and titanium) coated patch antennas with DGS (defected ground structure), patch fabricated on flexible substrates and other various techniques are adopted in this study. The other antenna parameters such as return loss (RL), VSWR and radiation pattern are also discussed in this chapter four with its references.

The conclusion remarks drawn from this study are highlighted in chapter five. The futuristic scope for further investigation is also included in this chapter.

Some of the important results obtained out of this research work have been published in peer reviewed International and National Journals, Proceedings of International and National Conferences/Symposia in India. The publications copies by the author are given at the end of this thesis.

Scope for further Improvement

The study reported here has opened for the following interesting points for future scope/investigations:

- The antenna characteristics may be improved further by fabricating these antennas on low loss RT Duroid materials and PTFE dielectric materials.
- The parasitic patch may be used around the radiator patch element for still more enhancement in impedance bandwidth.
- The study can also be done by changing the feed position from the edges towards the various positions on the patch surface.
- Other different compact designs using metamaterials, EBG can also be worked upon.
- The study can also be extended to the usage of new type of nanomaterial so as to enhance the performance of antennas.
- The concept of Electromagnetically gap coupled antennas with different feed pattern can be used to obtain better performance in terms of polarization aspects
- It is not necessary to do a more thorough analysis of different field solvers and simulators (such as Sonnet, AWR, HFSS etc.). We could only rely on the tool for the simulation using Mentor Graphics IE3D EM simulator.
- The study can also be elaborated to the concept of patch arrays and MIMO antennas suitable for steering the beam in specific direction, so as to reduce the unnecessary wastage of power levels and make the antenna efficient.

(Dr. Ambresh P Ambalgi)

References

- [1]. Poole P. Charles Jr., Owens J Frank., “*Introduction to Nanotechnology*” John Wiley & sons - India edition, 2006.
- [2]. Ashutosh Sharma, Jayesh Bellare, and Archana Sharma, “Advances in Nanoscience & Nanotechnology” NISCAIR (CSIR) publication, July 2004.
- [3]. Alen Rae, “Real Life Applications of Nanotechnology in Electronics,” *Special report, OnBoard Technology, Microsystems and Nanosystems*, pp. 36-39, Oct. 2005.
- [4]. V Ermolov, M Heino., A Karkkainen, N Nefedov, P Pasanen, Z Radivojevic, M Rouvala, T Ryhanan, E Seppala, M A Uusitalo, “Significance of Nanotechnology for future wireless devices and communications”, *the 18th Annual IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC'07)*, 2007.
- [5]. G. Sundararajan and Narasinga Tata Rao, “Commercial prospectus for nanomaterials in India,” *Jr. Of Indian Inst. Of Sci.*, Vol. 89, No.1, Pp. 35-41, Jan-Mar. 2009.

List of paper publications in Peer reviewed, Referred, Indexed list of International & National Journals, Conferences and Symposia

List of Ten first Author Publications in peer reviewed journals only (with ISSN) after obtaining Ph.D. in APA format : (N >= 10)

1. **Ambresh, P.A.** Hadalgi, P.M. Hunagund, P.V. & A.A, Sujata. (2014). Rectangular Microstrip Antenna With Slot Embedded Geometry. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (INDIA) Springer Series B*, 95(3), 213-217. ISSN: 2250-2106 (print version), ISSN: 2250-2114(Online). DOI: 10.1007/s40031-014-0090-3. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:11115.
2. **Ambalgi, Ambresh.** A.A, Sujata. & Chapi, Sharanappa. (2018). *Experimental & Simulation Study of Multiband Pentagon Slot Antenna for Wideband Applications. Journal of The Instrument Society of India*, 47(04), 109-112. ISSN: 0970-9983.UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:45516.
3. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (Feb.2019). Novel Multi-slotted Stripline fed Patch Antenna with Wideband Characteristics for Wireless Applications. *ICFAI-IUP Journal of Telecommunication*, 11(01), 01-08. ISSN:0975-5551.UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:63490.
4. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata.& Hunagund, P.V. (Jan. 2014). Design & Evaluation of Hexaband Microstrip Antenna. *International Journal of Current Research & Review*, 6(7), 86-90. ISSN (P): 2231-2196, ISSN (O): 0975-5241. IC Value: 4.18. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:2828/ 62702.
5. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (April.2014). L and X Band Rectangular Microstrip Antenna for Wireless Applications. *Journal of the Instrument Society of India*, 44(1), 65-67. ISSN: 0970-9983. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:45516.
6. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. (May 2015), Novel Compact Circular Patch Antenna Embedded with Rhombus Slot for 1 GHz -15 GHz Frequency Range. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering (IJARCSSE)*, 5(5), 1048-1050. ISSN: 2277-128X. (Impact Factor: 4). SCI value: 6.39.
7. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. & Hunagund, P.V. (Feb. 2014). Novel Pentaband Microstrip Antenna for 1 GHz -15 GHz Frequency Range. *International Journal of Advanced Research (UK)*, Vol.2, No.2, pp.414-418. ISSN (Online):2320-5407. (Impact Factor (JCC): 1.659, IC value: 4.96).
8. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (Dec 2014). Strip-line fed MicroPatch Antenna for Wideband Applications. *Journal of the Instrument Society of India*, 44(4), 267- 270. ISSN: 0970-9983.UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:45516.
9. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (Feb.2019). Double Octagonal Shape Microstrip Antenna. *International Journal Research in Engineering and Technology*,3(3), 31-34. Impact Factor-1.6. ISSN (O):2319-1163, ISSN (P): 2321-7308. DOI. 10.15623/ijret-2014.0315007.

10. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. Khan, A.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (Sept.2014). Quad Band Rectangular Microstrip Antenna for S and C-Band Applications. *International Journal of Computer & Communication Engineering*, 3(5), 334-337, ISSN: 2010-3743. (Paris based journal)
11. **Ambresh, P.A.**(May 2016). Coaxial Fed Microstrip Slotted Patch Antenna for Wideband Applications. *International Journal of Advancement in Engineering technology, Management and Applied Science*, 03(01), 271 -274. ISSN: 2349-3224. Impact Factor: 3.102.
12. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. S. Jagadeesha, Hadalgi, P.M. Hunagund & P.V. (Oct.2016). Design and Study of Pentagonal, Square Slotted Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications. *International Journal on Emerging Technologies (IJET)*, 7(2), 5-7, ISSN (Online): 2249-3255, ISSN (Print): 0975-8364. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:64147.
13. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. & Hunagund, P.V. (March 2017). **Novel Wide Slot Microstrip Antenna with Finite Ground Plane for 6 GHz to 16GHz**. IJRE – International Journal of Research in Electronics, 04(01), 48-50, ISSN(Print): 2349-2511 ISSN ONLINE: 2349-252X.Global I.F:1.28. Indexing: Academia, ProQuest, University Libraries etc.,
14. **Ambalgi, Ambresh P, S K, Sujata.** (2020). Study of Microstrip Patch Antenna Characteristics with Multi-slots Etched on 1.6mm thick Epoxy Dielectric Substrate. Science Direct: Materials Today journal, Elsevier publisher. 2020. ISSN: 1369-7021: IF:24.37. Scopus Indexed **(Accepted & In press)**.
15. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. (2018) Simulation and practical analysis of size miniaturized multiband pentagon, L-shape microstrip slot antenna. *Indian Journal of Radio and Space Physics*, 47, 61-65. (ISSN: 0975-105X (Online), ISSN P: 0367-8393. (Impact Factor- 0.89). UGC approved journal sl.no:1/2, Journal no:20869/20870.

List of Joint Author Publications during/after Ph.D. in APA format : (M)

1. D.N, Chandrappa. **Ambresh, P.A.** & Hunagund P.V. (July 2013). Varactor Diode Loaded Double Square Reconfigurable Microstrip Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications. *International Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering and Technology*, 4(4), 226-231. ISSN: 0976-6472. (Impact Factor- 5.6).
2. D.N, Chandrappa. **Ambresh, P.A.** & Hunagund P.V. (Aug. 2013). Design of Compact Reconfigurable Microstrip Antennas for Multi Frequency Wireless Applications. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering (IJARCCE)*, 2(8), 3366-3370. ISSN: 2278 - 1021. ISSN (Print): 2319 – 5940, ISSN (Online): 2278 – 1021. (Impact Factor - 1.770). ISO 3297: 2007.
3. D.N, Chandrappa. **Ambresh, P.A.** R.M, Vani. & Hunagund P.V. (2014). Multi-slots Reconfigurable Microstrip Antenna with Capacitive Loading Technique. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*. 2(1), 2632-2636. ISSN:**2320 – 9798(P)**, ISSN: **2320-9801(O)**. (Impact Factor: 1.386).ISO:3927-2007.

4. S, Jagadeesha. **P A, Ambresh.** Raj, Bharath. & K, Madhusudhana. (Oct 2016). Plus Shape Fractal Antenna with EBG Structure for Wireless Communication. *International Journal on Emerging Technologies (IJET)*, 7(2), 14-20. ISSN (Online): 2249-3255, ISSN (Print): 0975-8364. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, Journal no:64147.
5. S, Jagadeesha. **P A, Ambresh.** C, Sharanappa. & M, Bharath Raj. (Dec 2017). Design & Study of Microstrip Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications Using HFSS. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, 05(12), 2294-2297. ISSN (Online): 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98. **SJ I.F:6.887**. UGC approved journal sl.no:1, 2. Journal no: 45842,44382.

Publications in International conferences

6. **P. A, Ambresh** (2017, May 27 - 28). Performance Study of Gain Enhanced Stripline-fed Quad-Square Shape Patch Antenna. *2nd National Conference on Recent Advances in Engineering and Technology (NCRAET-2017)*, 299-303. Organized by Dept. Of Electronics & Communication Engineering, Basavakalyan Engineering College, Bidar, Karnataka.
7. **P.A, Ambresh.** A.A, Sujata. Hunagund P.V. & Gani, Prakash. (2015, March 9-11) Multiband Pentagon Shape Microstrip Slot Antenna. *International Conference On Functional Materials @ Nanoscale: Concerns and Challenges (ICFMNCC-2015)*,36-37, Dept. of Physics, Chemistry & Electronics Karmaveer Bhaurao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Pandharpur, Dist- Solapur (M.S.) – India. (ISBN: 978-81-930740-0-8).
8. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (2015, Nov.17-18). Experimental Study on Multiband Arrow Shape Patch Antenna with Inverted V-Slot. *International conference on Science & Engineering Research 2015 (ICSER 2015)*, 20, organized by GRDS, Singapore.
9. **Ambresh, P.A.** A.A, Sujata. S, Jagadeesha. Hadalgi, P.M. & Hunagund, P.V. (2015, Nov.11-13). Design and Study of Pentagonal, Square Slotted Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications. *First International Conference on Recent Innovations in Engineering and Technology-2016 (ICRIET-2016)*. 01-05. Bhemmanna Khandre Institute of Technology, Bhalki, Bidar. (ISBN: 978-81-932697-0-1).
10. **Ambalgi, Ambresh P.** S K Sujata. & Arthi Vaish (2019, March 13-14). Effect of Multi-slots on Patch Antenna characteristics Etched on Glass Epoxy Dielectric Material for Wideband Applications. *International Conference on IoT, Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud in Computational Vision and Bio-Engineering (ISMAC - CVB 2019)*, Vivekananda College of Technology for Women, Tamil Nadu, India.
11. **P. A, Ambresh.** A.A, Sujata. S, Jagadeesha. D N, Chandrappa. Hadalgi, P. M. & Hunagund, P.V. (2016, February 27). Multislotted Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications. *1st National Conference on Recent Trends in Communication and Computing (NCRTCC-2016)*, 33. Jain Institute of Technology, Davangere.
12. S, Jagadeesha. **P.A, Ambresh.** & Raj, Bharath. (2016, March 23 - 24). Size Reduction of Rectangular Microstrip Patch Antenna with Koch Fractal ground plane. ***National Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering Sciences and Management (NCESM-2016)***, Organized by Shridevi Institute of Engineering and Technology (SIET),73, Tumakuru, Karnataka. (ISBN:978-81-923066-6-7).

13. **P A, Ambresh.** A.A, Sujata. & Chapi, Sharanappa. (2018, Sept. 29). Study of Circular with horizontal Slotted Antenna for High Frequency Applications. *One day National Conference on Instrumental Methods of Analysis*, Organized by Dept. Of Chemistry, KLE Society's Jagadguru Tontadarya College, Gadag-Betageri, Gadag, Reaccredited with "A" grade by NAAC, Gadag, Karnataka. (Best Oral Presentation Award).
14. **P A, Ambresh.** B, Adithya. K.M, Gireesha. P.N, Sanjay. (2015, Jan 29-30). Design of Simple Circular Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications, National Conference on Recent Trends in Modern Electronics and its Applications 2015, (NCRTMEA 2015), *Jeppiaar Institute of Technology, Sriperumbudur, Chennai-631604*, pp. 12- 15.
15. **P A, Ambresh.** K, Chaithrasarawathi. B, Niveditha. (2015, Jan 29-30). Simulation Study on Square Patch Antenna for Wireless Application, National Conference on Recent Trends in Modern Electronics and its Applications 2015, (NCRTMEA 2015), *Jeppiaar Institute of Technology, Sriperumbudur, Chennai-631604*, pp. 1- 4.
16. **P A, Ambresh.** K.M, Gireesha. B, Adithya. P.N., Sanjay. (2015, Jan 29-30). 2.4 GHz Circular Patch Antenna for Wireless Applications, National Conference on Recent Trends in Modern Electronics and its Applications 2015, (NCRTMEA 2015), *Jeppiaar Institute of Technology, Sriperumbudur, Chennai-631604*, pp. 5- 8.
17. **P A, Ambresh.** B, Niveditha. K, ChaithraSaraswathi. (2015, Jan 29-30). "6 GHz Square Patch Antennas for Narrowband Wireless Applications", National Conference on Recent Trends in Modern Electronics and its Applications 2015, (NCRTMEA 2015), *Jeppiaar Institute of Technology, Sriperumbudur, Chennai-631604*, pp. 9- 11.
1. **Patent:** Patent filing number/ publication number: **201941038050**: Title of Invention: "**A RECTANGULAR MICROSTRIP ANTENNA DESIGN USING LOW-COST FR4 DIELECTRIC MATERIAL**": Filing date: 20/09/2019. Docket no.:79612, CBR.No.:30802.

(12) PATENT APPLICATION PUBLICATION	(21) Application No.201941038050 A
(19) INDIA	
(22) Date of filing of Application :20/09/2019	(43) Publication Date : 27/09/2019

(54) Title of the invention : A RECTANGULAR MICROSTRIP PATCH ANTENNA DESIGN USING LOW COST FR4 DIELECTRIC MATERIAL

(51) International classification	:H01Q9/00	(71)Name of Applicant :
(31) Priority Document No	:NA	1)DR.AMBRESH PRABHAKAR AMBALGI
(32) Priority Date	:NA	Address of Applicant :Assistant Professor, Dept of P.G.
(33) Name of priority country	:NA	Studies & Research in Electronics, Mangalore University,
(86) International Application No	:NA	Mangalagangothri. 574199, Mangalore. Karnataka. India
Filing Date	:NA	Karnataka India
(87) International Publication No	: NA	(72)Name of Inventor :
(61) Patent of Addition to Application Number	:NA	1)DR.AMBRESH PRABHAKAR AMBALGI
Filing Date	:NA	
(62) Divisional to Application Number	:NA	
Filing Date	:NA	

(57) Abstract :

The present invention is related to a novel rectangular microstrip antenna. Particularly, the disclosure of the present invention discloses a new and improved rectangular microstrip antenna (RMA) design with improving different aspects of rectangular microstrip antenna including use of different techniques. It presents an improved designed at S - band frequency of around 3.80 GHz and are fabricated using low cost FR4 dielectric material having $\epsilon_r = 4.4$ for two different thickness of dielectric material (0.16 & 0.24 cm). The plurality numbers of slits on the radiating patch edges of rectangular microstrip antenna is introduced which appear to have discontinuity with the microstrip transmission line and provide transverse component of current, which generates a longitudinal component of the magnetic field and can be modeled as series inductance

No. of Pages : 21 No. of Claims : 6